

CO-MINGLED THERMOPLASTIC PREPREGS INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The application of high strength, directionally reinforced thermoplastics has been severely limited due to the high cost of these materials with respect to the economics of most industries.

Vetrotex, the international glass fibre manufacturer within the St. Gobain Group, has developed a low cost process for the manufacture of co-mingled, glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic prepregs. These new precursor products, incorporating low cost thermoplastics, possess mechanical characteristics equivalent to thermoset composites with processing and recycling possibilities typical of thermoplastics.

Various novel application strategies will be developed based on either the low pressure processing capability of these materials or synergies with other thermoplastic materials.

INTRODUCTION

After about 25 years of industrial application of injection-moulded thermoplastics reinforced with glass fibres below critical length, the last six years has witnessed rapid growth in the industrial use of the so-called long fibre reinforcement materials.

This growth is particularly true for the GMT-type materials, which represent world-wide 60 kT per annum and a growth rate of about 20%. Future growth can also be expected with the new extruder-processed, long fibre products and systems that are also being developed and exploited.

These materials are progressing in volume because the industrial economic requirements are being met through a combination of materials cost and short cycle times. However, more rapid growth is being limited by their low levels of glass fibre reinforcement, typically 40 weight % or less.

Alternatively, high reinforcement levels can be obtained with woven reinforcements impregnated with thermoplastic by various means. Unfortunately, their high cost has prevented their penetration of industrial applications except for aerospace niche markets.

Vetrotex has recently developed a woven fibre thermoplastic product that meets both the high reinforcement level and the industrial economic requirements.

PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

VETROTEX has invented and developed a direct process for the manufacture of so-called co-mingled tows composed of interdispersed E glass and thermoplastic filaments, commercialised under the trade mark: TWINTEX.

This long fibre product form has existed before, but the new manufacturing process has considerably reduced product cost. As a direct result of cost reduction, the use of commodity or industrial thermoplastics becomes logical.

This paper will concentrate on the glass/PP prepreg for which product development has been completed. Similar products based on LLDPE and PET are under development.

The new co-mingling process also has the advantage of being able to produce a fine interdispersion of the two filament types, glass and thermoplastic. This point is illustrated in the SEM image of a co-mingled tow section (impregnated with a resin for observation purposes) shown in Fig. 1 for glass filaments (17 microns and white) and PP filaments (24 microns and black). The interdispersion fineness is critical for both processing and composite quality considerations.

The processing window, time-temperature-pressure, is highly dependent on the mass transfer distance that the molten thermoplastic must attain in order to completely penetrate the glass filament bundles. As shown in Fig. 1, the mass transfer distance is typically 20 to 40 microns.

Fig. 2 shows a pressure - temperature processing window based on a maximum void criterium and a 1 min. holding time. With increased processing times, the window will translate towards lower pressures to the point where moulding can occur at pressures somewhat less than 1 atmosphere.

Other means of associating reinforcement and thermoplastic filaments, such as co-twisted tows or co-woven fabrics, possess processing windows displaced towards higher pressures, temperatures and times because the mass transfer distances for composite formation are much greater.

The composite mechanical characteristics also will depend on the fineness and uniformity of the glass filament distribution within the matrix. In this respect, the capacity to achieve this optimal distribution is shown in Fig. 3 for a glass/PP system. Any deviation from an ideally uniform distribution can lower mechanical strength. For example, the development of a fibre bundle type of reinforcement distribution can lower flexure strength by as much as 25 %.

The impact resistance, tensile and flexural strengths for the glass/PP woven prepregs are shown in Fig. 4, 5 and 6. The mechanical characteristics are those of the 0° or 90° glass directions and are plotted as a function of the volume fraction of reinforcement in a particular direction. For example, a weave designed with 80 % glass content in the 0° direction and 20 % of glass content in the 90° direction and an overall glass content of 60 weight % (34 volume %) will have a tensile strength of 400 MPa in the 0° direction and 140 MPa in the 90° direction.

These data curves were established with inputs from six different laboratories which have processed and characterised the woven co-mingled fabrics. Unidirectional composite forms, such as calendared tapes or pultruded rods, tend to have considerably higher tensile and flexural strengths.

All the mechanical strengths and moduli (which obey the law of mixtures) show a linear response to increased volume % of glass reinforcement, except for the flexural strength where a saturation effect is evident.

The flexural failure for increased glass volume levels is that of compression, due to the buckling of the PP matrix. Preliminary results obtained for a PET matrix shows a linear response for flexural strength. This marked improvement can be attributed to the superior shear strength of the PET matrix.

PRODUCT APPLICATIONS

Various processing routes are open to co-mingled prepregs and these take into account the following characteristics, typical of directionalised or woven reinforcements.

* Co-mingled prepregs can be consolidated under low pressures, as low as 1 atmosphere.

- * As opposed to GMT or other non-directionalised precursors, woven precursors can be highly conformable but are non-extendable. That is, while a GMT material is designed to flow so as to fill out the mould cavity and create hydrostatic pressure, wovens do not possess these characteristics.
- * Synergies can be obtained between unreinforced thermoplastics or low level reinforced, flowable thermoplastics prepregs and highly reinforced, directionalised prepregs.

Compression moulding of woven co-mingled prepregs without a flowable material requires moulding tooling that will supply the necessary hydrostatic pressure in order to form complex shapes.

Fig. 7 shows a complex 10 kg part with a surface area of about 1.5 m², exhibiting vertical walls, undulating surfaces and stiffeners (battery tray for the Ford Ecostar electric car).

This battery tray was moulded using a vacuum technology, low cost tooling and a highly reinforced, drapeable, woven PP prepreg. Atmosphere pressure provided the necessary hydrostatic pressure for the moulding of this large, complex part.

Vetrotex is currently developing vacuum moulding technologies, based on woven co-mingled materials, as a cost-effective replacement technology for the current, environmentally precarious, contact or spray-up technologies using thermosets.

While a vacuum technology for thermoplastics is an attractive alternative to thermoset contact moulding for low volume, large part manufacture (ex. boat hulls), high volume manufacturing, say 1 part/min, typical of the automobile industry, could also be economically accessible to this technology through the use of multiple, but low cost tooling.

The economic advantage of production lines based on multiple, low cost tooling or a single, high pressure press with high cost tooling will depend on part size and complexity, production volumes, multiplicity of part variants and other factors concerning capital investment and cycle time.

Alternatively, a rubber stamping technology, employing somewhat higher pressures and the usual GMT processing route (preheating and cold mould), may be utilised whereby the part shape is provided by the metallic half of the mould and a quasi-hydrostatic pressure is assured by the elastomer half of the mould.

Fig. 8 shows a briefcase half-shell moulded in this way with IR preheating, 2 MPa moulding pressure and 1 min. mould cycle.

Another application objective currently under development exploits the potential synergy obtainable when flowable GMT materials are co-moulded with high strength woven co-mingled materials. The combination of the two materials results in a third material system that incorporates both excellent mouldability via the GMT process and high, directionalised strength.

As an illustration of this synergy, Fig. 9 shows the increase in impact strength as increasing volume fractions of woven material is added to the tensile side of a Charpy specimen, initially composed of a 100 % GMT material based on staple reinforcement.

As seen from curves of this type for impact, or other mechanical properties, a materials combination can be designed so as to attain a part performance level that satisfies a particular application requirement, unattainable with the GMT material alone.

In a similar materials strategy, development work is also being carried out with manufacturers of parts and semi-finished products composed traditionally of unreinforced thermoplastic. The synergy in these applications is even stronger than that for co-moulding with GMT because of the much greater difference between the mechanical properties of unreinforced thermoplastic and high strength, woven thermoplastic prepregs.

An excellent example of this strategy concerns the reinforcement of extruded polyolefin piping by hot overwrapping with linear preregs composed of the same polyolefin. Reinforcements of this type can increase the pressure bearing capacity of extruded piping by 3 to 4 fold with a reinforcement overwrap of only 10 volume %.

Clearly, because of the strength boosting power of high strength thermoplastic preregs with respect to unreinforced thermoplastics, the judicious incorporation of small volume fractions of the former into the latter, by various processes such as overwrapping, compression moulding, co-filament winding, etc, can expand considerably the initial product capability without detriment to cost effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

VETROTEX's new co-mingling technology has the potential to open up new composite material strategies through the combination of high strength, low cost and ease of processing.

The two strategies described in this paper should lead to industrial applications in the current contact markets, where VOC emissions standards being imposed necessitate replacement technologies or materials, as well as in existing thermoplastic applications where cost effective upgrading of mechanical properties can be realised.

Figure 1. Section of co-mingled tow showing fineness of intermingling between the glass filaments (17 microns, white circles) and PP filaments (24 microns, black circles).

Figure 2. Processing window for co-mingled glass/PP tow based on a minimum void criterium (courtesy IVW, Germany).

Figure 3. Micrograph of a composite section moulded from glass/PP co-mingled tows showing an even distribution of reinforcement resulting from fine scale co-mingling.

Figure 4. Linear response of impact energy absorption with increasing glass reinforcement level for composites moulded from woven glass/PP tows.

Figure 5. Linear response of tensile strength with increasing glass reinforcement level for composites moulded from woven glass/PP tows.

Figure 6. Non-linear response of flexural strength with increasing glass reinforcement level for composites moulded from woven glass/PP tows.

Figure 7. Large complex part (Ford Ecostar electric vehicle battery tray) moulded with co-mingled glass/PP fabric and a vacuum technology (Euro-Projects, England).

Figure 8. Thin walled part with vertical walls moulded with a cycle time of 1 min. and a rubber forming technology (TU Delft, Holland).

Figure 9. Charpy impact energy increase with increasing co-mingled fabric, 60 wt. % glass, combined (tension side) with a chopped fibre GMT, 40 wt. % glass (compression side)